

An Unexpected Find

Márcia Machado*, Marta Baptista, Carlos Fernandes, Jorge Cotter

Hospital Senhora da Oliveira, Guimarães

Citation: Márcia Machado, Marta Baptista, Carlos Fernandes, Jorge Cotter. *An Unexpected Find. Ann Med Res Pub Health. 2023;1(2):1.*

Received Date: 15 September, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 19 September, 2023; **Published Date:** 20 September, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Márcia Machado, Hospital Senhora da Oliveira, Guimarães

Copyright: © Márcia Machado, Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Ann Med Res Pub Health (AMRPH)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

CLINICAL IMAGE

A 55-year-old female patient complained about increased abdominal circumference and discomfort upon palpation. A computed tomography scan showed a 9 cm mass in her left adnexal region. The mass was removed and confirmed to be a mature cystic teratoma.

